

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 677622

Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas

Call: H2020-ISIB-2015-2

Innovative, Sustainable and Inclusive Bioeconomy

Work Programme: Topic ISIB-03-2015. Unlocking the growth potential of rural areas through enhanced governance and social innovation

Reporting on Bratislava

Social Innovation Think Tank (SITT) workshop

“Shaping social innovation for marginalized rural areas”

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1. FOREWORD

Scope of the event and workshop preparation

The first workshop of the Social Innovation Think Tank (SITT) on **26-28th October, 2016 in Bratislava (Slovakia)** brought together core project partners with the Scientific Advisory and Stakeholder Involvement Boards of SIMRA and discussed multi-faceted and complex challenges that our rural areas face. Common difficulties, such as transport, housing, ageing population, connectivity and regulations link up with global issues of climate change, sustainability, and energy and food security, that calling for immediate solutions, were considered in several rounds of stakeholder consultations. By engaging with stakeholders since the very beginning of project scientists wish to create a transparent and open-ended approach to problem framing. The workshop is therefore considered as an important starting point of the co-construction of SIMRA knowledge with stakeholders.

Thanks to the intense three months' preparation of the stakeholder consultations' content organised under the Task 2.3 of WP2 and supervised by Tatiana Kluvankova (IFE SAS), project coordinator Maria Nijnik and David Miller (JAMES HUTTON) and thanks to the active work and communication with the most of WP leaders through several skype meetings, workshop achieved the expected and planned results. However, it would not have been possible without active engagement of SITT members from the very beginning of the preparation period. SITT members were suggested by project partners and cordially invited by project coordinator Maria Nijnik to attend this event as well as to contribute to the project delivery. From 35 stakeholders addressed by sending invitation letter through email 20 came to the first workshop. To open the fruitful debate with SITT members about their perception and understanding of social innovations at the first meeting, Veronika Gezik (IFE SAS) conducted a short introductory survey through survey monkey (online research survey tool) from June to September 2016. Questions and detailed responses of the survey can be found in annex B. Smooth running of the workshop was ensured thanks to Stanislava Brnkalakova (IFE SAS) and the team of PhD students and other colleagues from SPECTRA – Centre excellence– joint research centre of the Institute of Forest Ecology Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovak University of Technology and Comenius University who served as local host of the event.

Overview and facts

The first SIMRA workshop was held under the transdisciplinary strategy of SIMRA project and coordinated by WP2. The aim of this 1st SIMRA Workshop was to develop and maintain systematic process of knowledge exchange and learning in understanding and assessing social innovations for marginalised rural areas with reference to the Mediterranean region. Engagement with stakeholders from the outset of SIMRA is crucial for the creation of a transparent and open-ended approach to producing socially innovative solutions to problems in Marginalised Rural Areas.

The workshop comprised opening and introduction, key note and 7 consultation sessions. Presentation slides have been published in PDF format and are available on the SIMRA website: <http://www.simra-h2020.eu/>. The detailed program of the workshop can be found in Annex A.

Day 1: Welcome and Introduction

The opening of the workshop took place in the aula of Slovak University of Technology where the attending of this event 26 colleagues from the SIMRA consortium (consisting of 26 partners from 15 countries) met for the first time with 20 members of the SOCIAL INNOVATION THINK TANK (SITT, i.e. the Scientific Advisory Board and the Stakeholder Involvement Board of SIMRA, consisting of European, Associated and non-EU experts in forestry, agriculture and rural development). The geographical distribution of the SITT members attending the event is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The geographical distribution of the SITT members attending the workshop

The heterogeneous audience ensured the concrete exchange of ideas between SITT members and project partners, the collection of ideas and expectations, and some fruitful outcomes from the round table discussions which will be detailed in the next sections.

Welcome and introduction was chaired by Tatiana Kluvánková, SPECTRA, Institute of Forest Ecology, Slovak Academy of Sciences. Introductory speeches were given by Robert Redhammer, President of the Slovak University of Technology, Ľubica Ditmarová, Director Institute of Forest Ecology, Slovak Academy of Sciences and Rastislav Rybanič, Director General Nature Conservation and Landscape Protection Ministry of the Environment. The workshop was also endorsed by the Slovak presidency of the Council of the European Union.

Maria Nijnik from The James Hutton Institute UK and SIMRA Coordinator, set up the scene by introducing the scope of the event as well as the SIMRA project ambitious work plan and expected results.

This short speech was followed by a participants' introduction workshop (Figure 2). The session was chaired by David Miller, The James Hutton Institute UK, who initiated dialogue on common understanding of marginalised rural areas. Participants indicated their expertise and interest using the future generation's vision of agriculture, forestry and rural areas that were painted by kids from a primary school in the SPECTRA neighbourhood (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 2: Stakeholders' introduction

Figure 3: The distribution of the SITT as per their category of expertise and interest

Figure 4: What are agriculture, forestry and rural development? Primary school students from Bratislava explained it with pictures

The last item of the agenda of Day one was a keynote presentation of Susan Baker from Cardiff University entitled 'Dynamics in Social Innovation: Enabling Factors and Barriers'. The presentation is available on the SIMRA website at the following address: http://www.simra-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/SusanBaker_keynote.pdf.

The work of Professor Susan Baker addresses social innovations and governance under global changes. She raised several challenging questions: *What are the overall and specific variables of the emergence of social innovation in marginalised rural areas? How do they affect a range of success factors and what are the lessons learnt in different rural areas? What are the most appropriate approaches, methods and tools that can be used for assessing social innovations? What does policy support to social innovation mean in different regional settings and contexts?* These questions framed the intense three days discussions under SIMRA's five thematic sessions with a particular reference

to the Mediterranean region. The presentation was followed by a long and constructive discussion. The key note presentation was given via video transmission.

Day 2: Social Innovations in Marginalised Rural Areas

The sessions on Thursday 27, 2016 took place in Bratislava's rural neighbourhood located at the cross border area with Austria at the confluence of Danube and Morava rivers and is surrounded by historical Devin Castle. A short walk was organised at lunch time during which a brief talk was given about cross border relations, the history of Devin municipality as well as the challenges and opportunities linked to isolation, marginalisation and current cooperation.

The consultation sessions of WP 2, 3, 5 and 7 with discussion rounds in breakout groups and plenary sessions for each consultation engaged both the SIMRA partner and SITT members in active exchange. Participants were stimulated to work interactively in small groups, organised in thematic sessions:

- **Stakeholder consultations I and II – Understanding and assessing social innovations and MRA (WP2 + WP3):** SITT members jointly identified the determinants (variables) that affect the emergence of SI in the forestry, agricultural and rural development and associated them with particular types of marginalised rural areas. They explored the dynamics that may influence diverging pathways of SI in different contexts in response to different local conditions.
- **Stakeholder consultations III - Introduction to SIMRA case studies (WP5):** The SIMRA case studies were introduced and the selection criteria for the case studies were discussed.
- **Introduction to the SIMRA communication (WP7):** SITT and SIMRA partners consulted on how to make the communication more interactive within the project but also with external stakeholders in order to engage the stakeholders in an active communication.

Day 3: Evaluation and Policies

The third day of the workshop took place at SPECTRA – Centre of excellence – where consultations of WP4 and 6 actively engaged both the SIMRA partners and SITT members. It was followed by a general plenary and a concluding session to the workshop.

- **Stakeholder consultations IV - Frameworks, methods and tools to assess social innovation and its impacts (WP4):** SITT members discussed the most appropriate frameworks, approaches, methods and tools that can be used for assessing social innovation in the economic, social, environmental, and governance/institutional domains.
- **Stakeholder consultations V - Policies and supporting actions for Social Innovation (WP6):** SITT members discussed the drivers of community driven innovation activities as well as the meaning of policy support to social innovation and the challenges to overcome.

Participating SITT organizations

Throughout the project, the SITT will represent a multilevel transdisciplinary structure comprising the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and the Stakeholders Involvement Board (SIB) consisting of European, Associated & non-EU actors and experts in forestry, agriculture and rural development. Engagement of the SITT members since the beginning of SIMRA has been recognised as crucial for the creation of a transparent and inclusive approach to the framing of social innovation in marginalised rural areas.

The Agrarian School of Coimbra in Portugal (ESAC), is a state-run polytechnic higher education school of agriculture. It develops scientific and technological knowledge in the areas of natural resources, food science, environment and sustainable development (more: <http://portal.esac.pt/portal/>).

The Centre of Arab Women for Training and Research (CAWTAR) was created in 1993 under the auspices of His Royal Highness, Prince Talal Ibn Abdulaziz, in response to the desire of a number of Arab governments, local and regional civil organizations, and regional and international institutions to establish a centre for academic research and field studies relating to the status of women (more: <http://www.cawtar.org/>).

The Business Centre of Innovation and Scientific, Technical and Economic Information of the National University "LVIVSKA POLYTECHNIKA" <http://www.lp.edu.ua/en> provides the development of innovational ideas and projects connecting scientists, students, and business representatives, and commercialization and promotion of results. It is a partner in the EU/UNDP framework project "Community Based Approach to Local Development". The project targets local communities implementing social-economic initiatives to become more energy efficient, promote circular economy and improve medical care <http://cba.org.ua/en/>

Department of Agricultural economics and Rural development of the University of Maribor in Slovenia concerns with mankind and sustainable development. One of its research field is land abandonment in mountain regions and the implementation of Rural Development Programs in mountainous regions (more: <https://www.um.si/Strani/default.aspx>).

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Gruppo di Azione Locale Prealpi e Dolomiti is a Local Action Group of the LEADER EU program that is devoted to community engagement process in the new strategy of local development (more: <http://www.gal2.it/>).

Ecosystem services community Scotland (ESCom) is an inclusive and open community with a wide constituency spread across Scotland. It aims to provide a coherent overview of the current understanding about ecosystem services and any potential knowledge gaps, to address the barriers to decision-making, and to identify relevant decision support tools (more: <http://escom.scot/>).

The overall objective of the **European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development (Evaluation Helpdesk)** is to contribute to the improvement of evaluation of EU rural development policy. The Evaluation Helpdesk is one of the two support units of the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) and works under the guidance of DG Agriculture and Rural Development (more: <https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/>).

The ENRD Contact Point (CP) is one of the two support units facilitating the work of the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD), along with the European Evaluation Helpdesk for Rural Development. Based in Brussels, a core permanent team is complemented by a larger group of experts, offering knowledge and facilitation in a wide range of rural development fields

(more at: https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/contact/enrd-contact-point_e).

European Forum on Nature Conservation and Pastoralism (EFNCP) is the only European organisation focusing on the maintenance of low-intensity livestock farming and maintaining a viable economic future for High Nature Value farming across Europe. EFNCP's network is uniquely positioned to provide a direct link between local projects involving low-intensity farming, and policy-making processes at national and EU levels (more: <http://www.efncp.org/>).

A new alliance in support of pastoralism in Spain, **Network Spanish Platform for Extensive Livestock Systems and Pastoralism** is opening the path to integration between agricultural and environmental policies. (more: <http://www.ganaderiaextensiva.org/>)

Faculty of Education at the Catholic University in Ruzomberok, Slovakia is focused on the development of innovative methodological approaches aiming to enhance the efficiency of environmental management and sustainable use of natural resources as well as the exchange of good practice examples about governing cultural and natural heritage. It is also involved in the creation of adaptation strategies for natural and social disturbances at local and regional levels.

The Science for the Carpathians (S4C) initiative is a regional science network targeting mountain research in the Carpathians aiming to create an active network of mountain researchers interested in interdisciplinary and international research collaboration, in developing the scientific community and in building research capacity in the region (more: <http://carpathianscience.org/>).

The Spanish Network for Rural Development (REDR) is a non-profit making association with the general aim of promoting a global and sustainable model of rural development. The REDR, national LEADER network, is currently made up of Regional Networks, which include over 200 Rural Development Groups throughout Spain (more: <http://www.forumagricolturasociale.it/>).

The Technology Agency of the Czech Republic is an organizational unit of the state that was founded in 2009 by the Act No. 130/2002 Coll. for the support of research, experimental development and innovation (more: <https://www.tacr.cz/index.php/en/>).

The Thünen Institute of Farm Economics is focused on the question of how political decisions affect farms and how they can adapt to the related changes in framework conditions. The institute's research focus is on the Germany-wide assessment of the impact of changing conditions on production, land use, income and environment in differently structured farms (more: <https://www.thuenen.de/en/bw/>).

The ECOREC Economic Research and Consulting firm (ECOREC) is focused on a better understanding of complex social issues, agricultural innovation systems and assessing the impact of agricultural research, technology and innovation policies in food security (more: <http://www.ecorec.org>).

University of Tuscia Libera, Italy focuses on rural development programs creation and land appraisal and management (more: <http://www.unitus.it/>).

Cairo University – the Faculty of Medicine seeks to combine the provision of high quality health care with innovative research and awareness rising in the field including in marginalised rural areas of the country. Recently, community based learning and research became very appealing to the medical students.

The **Ladies Right** NGO of Egypt supports innovation with its relevance to gender equality and women's rights.

2. REPORT FROM CONSULTATION SESSIONS: What have we achieved?

SESSION I (WP2-3): “Understanding and assessing social innovations and MRA”

Facilitators: Tatiana Kluvankova (IFE SAS/SPECTRA) (cross-coordination), Andrej Udovc (CETIP), Nico Polman (WUR), Bill Slee (Rural Development Company; Emeritus Fellow at The James Hutton Institute), Rosalind Bryce (Perth College)

Rapporteurs: Carla Barlagne (The James Hutton Institute), Viera Baštáková (IFE SAS/SPECTRA), Martin Spacek (SPECTRA-CETIP)

Objectives of the first consultation

The aim of this session was to identify the determinants (variables) that affect the emergence of Social Innovation (SI) in the forestry, agricultural and rural development and associate them with particular types of marginalised rural areas.

Methodology

The work was organised in focus group discussions followed by a plenary session. At the beginning of the session, a selection of variables that derived from the SITT survey (using Survey Monkey software) and a theoretical framework for the analysis of Socio-ecological systems (McGinnis and Ostrom, 2012) was presented to the participants.

The group discussions were organised in three subgroups according to the following fields of interest: agriculture, forestry and rural development. SITT members in round of focus group discussions selected and proposed new variables that affect the emergence of SI in the forestry, agricultural and rural development, and associated them with particular types of marginalised rural areas (e.g. mountains, arid areas, islands and sparsely populated areas).

For each sector, two examples of possible MRA related themes were provided to start up and stimulate the discussion about possibilities for SIs in practice:

Agriculture:

- 1) Social farming as a SI to increase the competitiveness of small scale farming,

2) Eco-farming

Forestry:

- 1) Ecosystem services as a SI to multifunctional forestry (carbon forestry for mountain regions),
- 2) From fire to bioenergy

Rural development:

- 1) Education for vulnerable groups in isolated areas,
- 2) Agro-tourism

Participants had the possibility to adjust these examples or suggest new ones and each group built the discussion on the following questions:

- 1) Can you describe the SIs in your example?
- 2) Which variables of emergence of SI are relevant in your example? Please select from the list.
- 3) What other variables would you consider?
- 4) What are the barriers, success factors and lessons learned in SI?
- 5) What do the SI examples have in common and how do they differ?

Main results

Overall the understanding of SI in marginalised rural areas was perceived in a very dynamic perspective. First, the sectoral division (forestry, agriculture, rural development) was found problematic and SITT gave preference to a comprehensive understanding of SI in MRA types of the region. Results indicate that classification and analysis of divergence of SI should be based on a complexity and problem solving perspective and was prioritised compared to a sectorial approach as can be seen from Figure 5 and Figure 6.

Figure 5: Focus group discussion on emergence of SI in sectorial examples

Next, most of the examples helped to identify variables that were relevant to most situations of emergence of SI. Additional variables, specific to each case were also recorded. After the workshop the variables selected by SITT members were later compared with the literature review.

The selected examples of social innovations were used in the next session, where SITT members identified and characterised SI examples into more details while linking them with challenges in each area.

Figure 6: Posters of the three focus group discussions: a) Social Farming (in Arid Areas), b) Accessibility of Health Care (in Sparsely Populated Areas), c) Polycentric Network Approach to Forest Fire Management (in Mountains Areas)

SESSION II (WP 2-3): “Understanding and assessing social innovations and MRA”

Facilitators: Rosalind Brice (cross-coordination, Perth College), Martin Price (Perth College), David Miller (The James Hutton Institute), Andrej Udovc (CETIP Network), Elena Górriz

Rapporteurs: Carla Barlagne (The James Hutton Institute), Martin Spacek (CETIP Network/SPECTRA), Diana Valero (Perth College), Nico Polman (WUR)

Objectives of the second consultation

This session had two main objectives: 1) to get examples of different types of SI and link them with different types of MRA; and 2) to start building preliminary hypotheses about dimensions of SI emergence and divergence.

Methodology

Following session I, consultations of session II focused on selecting SI examples in a different type of MRA: islands, sparsely populated areas, mountains, and arid areas organised in four round tables. The session was developed in four stages around two main activities (participatory mapping and hypotheses building discussion). First, there was a brief outline of the session by Rosalind Bryce who introduced the work done with the MRAs and the objectives of the session as well as how the proposed activities engaged with the work done in the previous session. Then, the participatory mapping activity began with SITT members working in groups with MRA maps identifying and characterising SI examples while linking them with challenges in each area. This activity was developed using provisional maps of the MRAs in the different regions covered by the project. Next, the work in groups continued with a hypothesis building discussion about following variables SI divergence in and between MRAs which was recorded on flip charts. Finally, there was a carousel activity with the groups circulating to give feedback on the work developed by the other groups.

Main results

With regards the exploration of different types of SI and their development in different types of MRAs, the results showed the following ideas:

- Geographical diversity of SI: The category of SI the more represented across different regions was biodiversity conservation which is present in all regions in Europe and nearly all types of MRAs (no examples were mentioned for arid areas). The category of SI present in all types of MRAs was sustainable agriculture. However, examples raised were all from Southern Europe, Western Europe and Non-EU Mediterranean. The areas with more diversity of SI were islands and sparsely populated areas (7 categories both of them). Mountain areas reported examples in 6 different categories; and arid areas had 5. These trends are of course a reflection of those SITT members in each group and are only a starting point for understanding diversity.
- In addition to the proposed categories of SI (commons, education, sustainable agriculture, biodiversity conservation, renewables, cooperatives, social farming, local food, and Leader approach) - two 'new' categories were introduced: women empowerment initiatives in arid areas in non-EU Mediterranean countries; and examples related to arts, craft, and creativity spread in islands and sparsely populated areas in Northern Europe and Eastern Europe.
- SITT members made some comments on the MRA mapping work currently in progress. These comments are being taken into account as the MRA mapping progresses.

Besides, the examples provided by the SITT members during the activities enabled us to identify 18 new SI cases that were added to the SIMRA database which will be online next spring.

Concluding remarks from SESSION I and II and plenary

The work developed during the sessions was very successful thanks to the engagement and participation of all the SITT members in the proposed activities. Interesting results were gathered regarding the two pursued objectives. In particular, two important aspects were received that will significantly contribute to the SIMRA understanding of social innovations in marginalised rural areas.

At first there are MRA type specific processes where SI emerge or are socially needed. Such as:

- **Mountain areas:**
 - SI examples were reported for the following categories: Education, Sustainable Agriculture, Biodiversity Conservation, Cooperative, Social Farming, and Local Food.
 - The existence of distinctive traditions, food, or cultural diversity jointly with the availability of resources, including public funds are key variables for the emergence of SI in this type of MRA.
- **Islands:**
 - SI examples were reported for the following categories: Commons, Sustainable Agriculture, Biodiversity Conservation, Cooperatives, Social Farming, Leader, and Arts & Crafts.
 - Environmental value jointly with other geographical factors or social problems are key variables for the emergence of SI in this type of MRA.
- **Sparsely Populated areas:**
 - SI examples were reported for the following categories: Commons, Education, Sustainable Agriculture, Biodiversity Conservation, Renewables, Cooperatives, and Arts & Crafts.
 - The presence of key actors, and informal networks underpinning territorial marketing jointly to both the training in entrepreneurial skills, and the link to other areas and communities are key variables for the emergence of SI in this type of MRA.
- **Arid areas:**
 - SI examples were reported for the following categories: Education, Sustainable Agriculture, Renewables, Leader, and Women empowerment.
 - The presence of social needs jointly with the territorial and social resources available, including the existence of networking are key variables for the emergence of SI in such MRA.

A second list of variables of SI emergence and divergence was derived from the focus group discussions in session I and confirmed the ones derived from the literature review (Table 1). This list is not an exhaustive but it gives an indication of the many variables within different categories used in literature, according to 1) social innovation environment, 2) innovation as a learning process/entrepreneurial activity, and 3) innovation adoption. Most relevant SI variables were validated in plenary and listed below.

Table 1: Variables of SI emergence and divergence

Innovation Categories	Suggested variables
SI environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participation/ Networking (community, equality) ● Motivation (legitimacy, income, helping people) ● Governmental support/ Feedback (legal, state, funds) ● Traditions, cultural diversity ● Need to adapt (survival after disturbance)
Innovation as learning process/ entrepreneurial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leadership (sharing visions, values) ● Self-organization (learning, social capital)

activities	
Innovation adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources (economic, social, environmental) • Global to local government (scale) • Property rights

The variables that determine the potential for SI to develop and can influence the rate of adoption of innovations, will be implemented in understanding SI and further developed in SIMRA diagnostic.

SESSION III (WP5): “Evaluation of social innovation case studies”

Facilitators: Elena Gorriz (EFIMED), Valentino Marini Govigli (EFIMED), Elisa Ravazzoli (EURAC), Rosalind Bryce (Perth College), Riccardo Da Re (UNIPD).

Rapporteurs: Carla Barlagne (Hutton), Diana Valero (Perth College), Andrej Udovc (CETIP Network), Martin Spacek (CETIP Network/SPECTRA).

Objectives of the third consultation

The purpose of this session was to understand the SITT preferences towards social innovation (SI) case studies. It was meant to get insights for preferential topics or case study aspects, beyond the technical selection criteria. The preferences were conceptualized as the characteristics that would compound their “ideal” case study.

Methodology

Divided in four small groups, SITT members were asked: **Which features do you think are important when selecting SIMRA case studies?** Features were articulated in the following dimensions: (i) Sub-fields within agriculture, forestry and rural development; (ii) Socio-economic problems/opportunities related to SI case study; (iii) Contextual factors facilitating/obstructing SI case study; (iv) Type of action related to SI case study; and (v) Internal decision-making process.

Each dimension counted with a series of alternatives. The field of rural activity contained an additional subdivision. By using cards, the stakeholder groups were asked to discuss and assess their preference related to the alternatives, as well as to add alternatives that they missed. Each group had to select five alternatives for each dimension.

Following the ranking resulting from the discussion round, a survey was built with the amended alternatives, structured according in a SMART-format (Simple Multi Attribute Rating Technique). SMART questionnaires require individuals to weight the list of alternatives, from the most important one (assigned 100 points), and assign proportionally smaller values to other alternatives. During the final wrap-up, the survey exercise was presented and delivered in paper form to be sent online.

Main results

1. Selection of case study features exercise

- Three out of four groups found difficulties to finish the exercise and only one group actually managed to complete it. The understanding of the exercise and the debate over the alternatives resulted too long for covering all the proposed dimensions.
- In general, the groups felt that all the options presented were somehow equally important (*“all are interesting!”*). Several SITT members pointed out to the complexity of ranking the non-dichotomous alternatives. Others brought up the difficulty to weight and select sensitive issues (e.g. type of vulnerable people in rural areas).
- Some groups felt that the given dimensions were not relevant for choosing case studies, especially in terms of the different sub-fields of rural activities (forestry, agriculture, rural development). That is, the emphasis is not so much on whether the farming activities are short-term (e.g. vegetables) or long-term (i.e. fruit trees), but on the nature of the problems SI aim to tackle and the manner the SI handles them.
- Overall, SITT members raised the point that the technical criteria should be prioritised to the stakeholder preferences and that they trust the scientific criteria to cover the diversity of features in a robust manner. This gives SIMRA consortium margin to focus on the technical aspects and get back to SITT members with the shortlist of case studies selected according to the technical criteria for the corresponding analyses.
- A group suggested reversing the exercise, describing potential case studies according to the listed criteria. This is actually the process that will be taken after the elaboration of the SI database (WP3).
- On the whole, emphasis was given to more sustainable modes of production (e.g. organic agriculture was preferred to conventional productive farming). Focus on vertical and horizontal integration of the rural value chains was equally felt relevant. As problems or opportunities, SITT groups preferred to analyse cases tackling diversification of rural products and services, as well as marketing challenges.

2. Survey results

Only four SITT members out of 21 replied to the survey that was distributed at the end of the workshop and sent back by the SITT members afterwards. Taking into account the small number of responses, the results are reported, as they coincide with the main outcomes of the group discussions:

- The **socio-economic problems** that social innovations attempt to tackle in MRA and **internal decision making process issues** were felt to be the most relevant for the selection of SIMRA CS (respectively 75 and 72.5 over 100).
- Within the specific socio-economic area, the issue of **rural versus urban reality** was selected as the most important characteristic (87.5 over 100) within which **job and market opportunities** (80) and **rural identity** (82.5) were felt to be the most relevant issues.

- In terms of the decision making process, respondents weighted the highest the alternative of **leadership issues and leadership accountability** (95).
- Some additional questions were asked to SITT regarding specific characteristics of the action to investigate. Respondents suggested focusing more on **group-lead SI** rather than individual lead, **private** rather than public, **consolidated actions** rather than recent (i.e. less than 5 years), and **success case** rather than failure cases.

SESSION IV (WP4): “Frameworks, methods and tools to assess social innovation and its impacts assessing”

Facilitators: Laura Secco, Elena Pisani, Catie Burlando, Riccardo Da Re (University of Padova)

Rapporteurs: Carla Barlagne (The James Hutton Institute), Martin Špaček (CETIP Network), Andrej Udovč (prof. CETIP Network), Diana Valero (Perth College)

Objectives of the fourth consultation

1. Identify the most appropriate and useful approaches, frameworks, methods and tools that can be used for assessing social innovation based on experience and expertise of the invited participants and stakeholders.
2. Understand the kind of outputs stakeholders would like to have from an assessment on social innovation in marginalized rural areas, e.g. what types of data and information, in which format, at what level.
3. Describe and classify the frameworks, methods and tools for assessing social innovation by domain (economic, social, environmental, governance/institutional).

Guiding questions

1. **WHAT:** What information would you like to obtain from an evaluation of social innovation?

2. HOW: If you were tasked, how would you evaluate social innovation?

Specific questions addressed at the round tables:

1. How would you measure SI?
2. What would you expect from those methods?
3. What are their pros and cons?

Methodology

A question on methods was first proposed to the SITT in the online survey in July 2016 (please refer to Annex C for the results of that survey). The activity was divided into 2 parts. During the first part of the session, the world café participatory approach was adopted. Four topics were discussed, focusing on issues related to approaches, assessment frameworks, methods and tools. The issues were the following:

- A. outcome-oriented vs. process-oriented evaluation methods
- B. participatory vs. experts-based evaluation methods
- C. primary and secondary data
- D. qualitative vs. quantitative methods

During the second part, participants were encouraged to write ideas for potential indicators that could be used to evaluate SI. The present report provides (i) a summary of the discussions in each table, (ii) a table summarising points of strengths and weakness identified by SITT members.

Main results

There were rich discussions in all four groups that highlighted the complementarity of the concepts proposed for the evaluation of social innovation and its impacts, as well as the strengths and weaknesses (see pictures below and Table 2).

In the **process-oriented vs. outcome-oriented evaluation methods**, members highlighted how the evaluation depends on whether SI is defined as a process or as a result. Others highlighted how the relationship between process and outcome is very important, and both need to be evaluated. Stakeholders also highlighted the importance of measuring the tangible and the intangible elements of SI in relation to process vs. outcome-oriented evaluation; and identifying the factors in the process that contribute to success or failure in the results. One the one hand, ex ante evaluation can help reflect on the strategy for selecting case studies for SI evaluation. On the other hand, there are different starting points for SI. The synergies and the SI spiral make it difficult to 'stop' and look at outcomes and results, and different national contexts mean that what is SI in one country may be standard practice in another.

For some members, **you should start with outcomes, and then identify the elements that led to failure or success**; while for others, **evaluation should start with the situation (context analysis), then the assessment**

of process and then of outcomes. In conclusion, it was agreed that the definition of SI is needed to decide what must be measured and how it should be done.

The discussions in the **participatory vs. experts-based evaluation** round table highlighted both strengths and weaknesses of the two types of evaluation, and supported complementarity between the approaches.

Examples were given to support the use of participatory processes (also led by experts) to legitimate, increase ownership and ultimately lead to adoption and implementation. The use of participatory approaches was also seen as **crucial for assessing the ‘feeling’ or intangible aspect of those who were involved in social innovation** (i.e. in the evaluation of LEADER) through indicators for measuring trust, the involvement of the community in innovative approaches, the connection to other actors and the level of acceptance and exchange of new practices. Among the risks of the participatory approaches was the loss of interest: **if you do not keep people involved during a participatory process, and follow up on their suggestions, then they will become less inclined to collaborate.** Participants also highlighted the importance of **evaluating the impacts of SI through actual changes in policy.** The group concluded that it was important to understand **“how you follow a story”**, and how you **look at long-term impacts of SI.**

In the **discussion on primary vs. secondary data**, the discussions highlighted the lack of secondary data on social innovation, as well as **the importance of primary data to identify the specific context of social innovation, and the need to use them both complementarily.** Stakeholders suggested the following methods for data collection: (i) focus groups and participatory methods; (ii) semi-structured interviews; (iii) long term survey for studying pre and post conditions; and (iv) stakeholder analysis, emphasising the importance for gathering soft data on interactions, feelings and activities. However, participatory approaches should also rely on critical approaches and capacity for reflection, to avoid the risks of subjective biases. The data could be collected internally or externally, but should be seen as a two-way communication process. Key indications were that, (i) data should be comparable; (ii) triangulation should be used to verify quality of data is required; and (iii) data should be publicly available.

In the discussion on **qualitative vs. quantitative methods**, SITT members agreed that evaluation methods and tools should be different and need to be properly tailored to: (i) the needs and purpose of the evaluation; (ii) the type of project that you are evaluating; and (iii) the object of measurement, e.g. whether it is a process or a “result or outcome”. Qualitative and quantitative approaches were identified as **complementary and suitable to the context of evaluation**: they are useful for triangulation and yield different types of results which support each other, by providing in-depth information on the process and results of a project.

It was agreed that the objectives and the framework for evaluation needs to guide the approaches and methods used, as well as the use of both internal and external evaluation. Quantitative methods are not always popular among practitioners but they are considered extremely useful (or fundamental) when discussing with and trying to convince policy makers and funders. On the other hand, qualitative methods provide you with in-depth information; e.g. it informs you about what different groups of stakeholders get from the project; their perception, and how they feel they benefit from the program. It was specified that they are necessary when describing results. Here, the evaluation might be based on a multi-criteria analysis involving combinations of indicators. At the same time, those indicators should be as synthetic as possible. Finally, it was noted that when dealing with small projects or very new and/or innovative projects, it might be difficult to measure the long term impact of the project.

Finally, SITT members suggested a preliminary list of indicators. These will be subject to further work and refinement with the stakeholders in a second phase. These indicators were general: *Quality of life, Quality of products before and after*; and more specifically related to networks: *Number of network members and change over time to measure the effects of policy interventions; Quality of linkages between network members to measure the sustainability of the network; Active/regular networks; connectedness of the network, Marginalization of members; Number of informal network in long term*. These also related to the structure of the network: *Number of different actors involved; Number of different sectors involved; Number of partners involved; Diversity of enterprises and number networks; Number of self-employed enterprises; Communication; Social return on investment*.

Table 2: Summary of the main points of strength and weakness identified by SITT members

<u>Outcome-based evaluation</u>	<u>Process-based evaluation</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fulfills political expectations • A limited set of indicators may be enough to measure the concrete results of a project, but may not be enough to identify it as a SI or not. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The important element in SI is process • Process-oriented evaluation is a learning process • It needs to rely on participatory approaches • Needs to focus on the informality of process • Needs to address motivation of participants in the evaluation processes
<u>Expert-based</u>	<u>Participatory-based</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid bias, strive for objectivity • More experience in evaluation • Credibility of report results • Can set recommendations derived from participatory approaches • Better for quantitative evaluations • Ensure validity of feedbacks in qual. methods • Increase confidentiality of personal opinions • Possible to generalize 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More effective from the perspective of end users • Can validate the results • Can be designed by experts • Ensures legitimacy • Enables to capture process • Ensures ownership of results • Enables bottom-up mobilization/lobbying • Allows to scale up results
<u>Secondary data</u>	<u>Primary data</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is data on economic and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SI is locally specific and needs primary data

<p>environmental impacts, but it is difficult to access and interpret (e.g. green energy)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on enterprises innovation is available in some countries but without an evaluation of impacts (e.g. Czech Republic – Innovation Survey) • It would be cheaper and already processed • Support analysis at the large scale (but need to define first at which scale the SI happens) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local data should be of broad use, for various purposes and relevant for policy and research • The focus should be on processes • “Soft data” is key: perceptions, visions, expectations/preferences, gaps • Analyse impact on different groups • Analyse “intermediate impacts” • Team and ongoing feedback; self-assessment • Data should be directly usable (easy to interpret), available, easy to use, freshly collected, reliable • A two-way communication process • Collected internally or externally?
<p><u>Qualitative methods</u></p>	<p><u>Quantitative methods</u></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More suited to measure SI because it explains how and why the project has been successful • Give in-depth information (descriptive) about a specific case study and about the process • Can be used to assess short-term impacts of project • BUT: can be subjective • Long training for the evaluator • More expensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easier to communicate to policy-makers • Easier to achieve measurement • Can be used for longer term impacts of project • BUT: can also be subjective depending on how you manipulate the data

SESSION V (WP6): “Policies and supporting actions for Social Innovation”

Facilitators: Robert Lukesch (Regional Development Consultant, ÖAR-Regionalberatung, Austria), Bill Slee (Rural Development Company; Emeritus Fellow, James Hutton Institute, Craigiebuckler, Aberdeen), Alice Ludvig (Senior Researcher, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, BOKU Vienna and EFI regional office Vienna) and Gerhard Weiss (Work Area Leader, BOKU Vienna and EFI regional office Vienna).

Rapporteurs: Carla Barlagne, (The James Hutton Institute), Martin Špacek (CETIP Network) and Viera Bastakova (IFE SAS/SPECTRA)

Objectives of the consultation

The main objective for this consultation was to obtain statements of evidence by key stakeholders and opinion leaders on the policies and fostering actions in support of Social Innovation. In the consultation the opinion and view of the SITT is a most valuable source of information and contribution to knowledge exchange and focused issue-framing for linking policy and practice in SIMRA. Thus, the following questions were addressed: What are the drivers of community-driven innovation activities and how can these be fostered? What does policy support mean to social innovation (SI) in different regional settings and contexts? How can SI be communicated and what are challenges to overcome?

Methodology

The consultation was designed as a multi-stakeholder dialogue event. To facilitate such a dialogue in a most participatory manner (Slocum 2003¹), it was necessary to split all participants into 3 small groups of around 8 members. In its methodological setting, the consultation was designed as a focus group amongst experts. A focus group is a sub-type of a discussion group interview; it is most suitable for an initial concept exploration and the generation of creative ideas on a specific topic. This suited the objective of collection of statements of evidence and to obtain input from stakeholders. The focus group has to be facilitated by a moderator; moderation guidelines were prepared, which consisted of clear, open-ended short and precise questions with simple wording. These were to be flexible used and adapted to the group's natural conversation by the three moderators.

In concrete terms, after a short introduction by Alice Ludvig to the main goals and the method, three heterogeneously mixed small groups were formed for a 70-minute consultation. The moderator guidelines were structured around the following three main questions:

- 1. What does **policy support** for Social Innovation mean to you?
- 2. How do you **communicate** it (SI)?
- 3. How are you involved in **fostering** SI?

After the three individual focus group sessions, all participants and the moderators met again for an exchange of information and short reporting on the outcomes in each group in a plenary session.

¹ Slocum, Nikki (2003): Participatory Methods Toolkit. A practitioner's manual, Belgian Advertising, Brussels.

Main results

Summary of key messages of all Focus groups:

- **Gentle support and dialogue needed**

Some of the participants urged that **support** is needed from Policy, but in a **gentle** mode. For all of them one main precondition is that policy makers understand what SI is about. For this, most importantly a **dialogue is necessary** between policy and social innovation activists. Other participants argued that sometimes the support seems a bit like lip-service to SI.

- **High Level Policies still with potential to intensify**

Some participants argued that there are **not many activities** on a high level. They reasoned that e.g. EIP (European Innovation Partnerships) and LEADER (Links between actions for the development of the rural economy) are both relatively inflexible and that LEADER was formerly less bureaucratic and more flexible. However, they claim that there is **ongoing and growing rhetoric** on the issue of Social Innovation at the macro level of EU politics. Action has yet to follow to the commitment.

- **Practitioners in the focus groups need policy makers with open minds**

Innovation and social innovation **need risk-taking**, thus there needs to be the will to also fund risk-taking projects with no assurance of immediate success. Social Innovation may often be risky and requires greater risk tolerance on the part of the funders. Also cross-sectoral money possibilities shall be available, for this policy makers must think outside their boxes of sectors.

- **Good communication of SI needs good and excellent examples.**

Convincing communication of SI is not easy and needs really well researched and excellent examples. It is considered really important to highlight and showcase good examples of showcase good examples of social innovation to key personnel in the policy community.

Short report of each Focus group

Group 1: Moderator Robert Lukesch

In this discussion group, many individual examples were brought up. The participants agreed that it is not top-down regulations that could solve all problems in rural areas. For them it is an idealistic belief that every problem can be solved with a regulatory policy instrument. Some brought examples that there are good rules, but they do not reach down to the beneficiaries in their implementation phase. Examples were brought from Tourism projects in the Czech Republic, agricultural innovation systems in Azerbaijan, the Spanish Rural development (RD) policies and the Local Action Groups (LAGs) there. Common denominators were identified for successful policy support: First, a dialogue and dialogue groups are necessary before any designing of policies at the higher levels. Second, the policy implementation has to persist also in times of (national) government changes. Third, especially and particular in marginalised rural areas (MRA), policies have to be more targeted. They have explicitly to focus on empowering and addressing people in challenging conditions.

Group 2: Moderator Bill Slee

Also in this group, many examples were brought up, it was argued that policy support can only give the opportunity to use the tools, e.g. municipalities should have open budgets for innovation and activities. Yet there are vast differences amongst countries (West and East, North and South) and some countries are still not familiar with all measures and tools. Especially communication and dissemination is important, but not only by using popular terms such as "SI" or "Climate Change", but to explain the particular challenges or issues as well

as successful outcomes and results. In the discussions, it turned out that there seems to be a lack of trust, even distrust amongst some institutional players themselves (between levels and sectors), and there is much diverging interest between stakeholders themselves. One possibility to overcome some of these challenges was identified to lie in personal contacts rather than systemic organisation. There was a strong consensus that greater clarity on what social innovation is was needed and of the key elements that make for effective social innovation as well as better showcasing of best practice.

Group 3: Moderator Alice Ludvig, rapporteur Gerhard Weiss

In this group many practitioners were present who are in day-to-day contact with policy makers. They identified three factors for success: First, supportive policy makers are good networkers who also provide useful information. Second, good communication is very important, by this is meant to spend time for regular exchange. Third, politicians have to visit the projects with press. All this needs continuous effort, large time and manpower investments. Examples were brought from Scotland and Ireland that showed that LEADER is too rigid and should be more open, transparent and especially “project friendly” in terms of risk-distribution. All participants agreed that policy has to be adaptive, reflexive and flexible and include feedback loops. A policy framework shall provide legitimacy to the action but the action comes from the region. However, some actions simply change the mutual environment and trust amongst communities and infrastructure in a region, this is difficult to report, as most monetary policy instruments are explicitly project based and want to measure the success of a single targeted project.

WP 7: “Introduction to the SIMRA communication”

Facilitators: Lucia Lopez Marco (IAMZ-CIHEAM), Antonio Lopez Francos (IAMZ-CIHEAM), Lauren Mosdale (Euromontana)

Rapporteurs: Lucia Lopez Marco (IAMZ-CIHEAM), Antonio Lopez Francos (IAMZ-CIHEAM), Lauren Mosdale (Euromontana)

Objectives of the WP7 consultation

The objective was to consult the SITT and other SIMRA partners on how to make the communication more interactive within the project but also with external stakeholders in order to engage the stakeholders in an active communication.

Methodology

WP7 presented the communication tools planned and those already in place (workshops, website, social media, brochure, newsletter, etc.) and directly interacted with the audience for feedback.

Main results

The creation of the SITT and the involvement of stakeholders from the beginning of the project were welcomed by all. Overall, using interactive methods in a project about social innovation is coherent and we are starting with a solid foundation on which to build. In this regard, **the intranet is an essential tool for internal SIMRA communication but also for the SITT**. Improvement is always possible in terms of interaction whether it be on **our website (more videos, podcasts, webinars, etc.)** or in the organization of **our events (display of information, presentation techniques, space organization, etc.)**. Also, **social media content could be more targeted**. This will naturally evolve when the SIMRA project publishes more results.

How to improve things?

- Starting by **meetings**, participants expressed the desire to know more about the other participants which could be done by **displaying pictures of participants** with their interests and links to social innovation (both partners and stakeholders) in the workshop room; and **inviting guests** to hear about their experiences/testimonies in SI and going on **field trips**. Considering the more technical aspects of the workshop, a more “flexible” organization was suggested such as having discussions in **an open space** so that participants could circulate and chose the issues they wish to discuss.
- About the communication tools, we could **record podcasts, webinars and videos** to present case studies with people from inside and outside the project in an interactive way on our website.
- Continuing with the **website**, some concrete suggestions were made such as differentiating SIMRA events from others in the News/Events section and adding a **Frequently Asked Questions** section.
- We were asked to promote the **blog** as a means of getting information and make connections between articles to find information more easily.
- In relation with WP3, there was a demand for a well-structured **database** of SIMRA related only case studies, with particular attention payed to community based case studies, not often reflected in institutional databases.
- Finally, about the **MOOC**, it was confirmed that its aim must be to “**train trainers**” who would in turn disseminated the knowledge to others. The question of SITT members mentoring the MOOC students remains open.

3. ANNEXES

Annex A: Social Innovation Think Tank members attending the event

name	organisation	country
Matteo Aguanno	Dolomiti e Prealpi bellunesi Local Action Group (LEADER EU program)	Italy
Rut Bizkova	Technological Innovation Agency	Czech republic
Andreja Borec	University of Maribor	Slovenia
Soukeina Bouraoui	CAWTAR	Tunisia
Jose Gaspar	Escola Superior Agraria De Coimbra	Portugal
Lubos Halada	Science for the Carpathians (S4C) International Mountain Network	Slovakia
Gwyn Jones	European Forum on Nature Conservation and Pastoralism (EFNCP)	UK
Maria Kozova	Katolicka Univerzita Ruzomberok	Slovakia
Omneya Lofty	Ladies' Rights Association	Egypt
Marc Metzger	Ecosystem Services Community Scotland	UK
Jabier Ruiz Mirazo	Spanish Platform for Extensive Livestock Systems and Pastoralism & EFNCP	Spain
Orest Mukha	Centre of Innovation and Information	Ukraine
María José Murciano	REDR (Red Española de Desarrollo Rural)	Spain
Mariana Nikolova	South Eastern Europe Mountain Research Network	Bulgaria
Magda Porta	European evaluation helpdesk for RD	Belgium
Ilaria Signoriello	Forum Nazionale Agricoltura Sociale	Italy
Paul Soto	ENRD Contact Point, Brussels	Belgium
Ahmed Taha	Department of Medicine, Cairo Univeristy	Egypt
Tugrul Temel	ECOREC	Turkey/Netherlands
Lorenzo Venzi	University of Tuscia and Libera	Italy

Annex B: Agenda of the Workshop

PROGRAMME

26. 10. 2016 Wednesday

location: Slovak University of Technology, Vazovova 5, 812 43, Bratislava

15.00 - 16.00 Registration, tea and coffee - University aula

16.00 - 18.00 Welcome and Introduction - chair: *Tatiana Kluvánková, SPECTRA, Institute of Forest Ecology, Slovak Academy of Sciences*

16.00 - 16.20 *Robert Redhammer, President of the Slovak University of Technology*
Ľubica Ditmarová, Director Institute of Forest Ecology, Slovak Academy of Sciences

Rastislav Rybanič, Director General Nature Conservation and Landscape protection Ministry of the Environment

16.20 - 16.40 **Introduction to the SIMRA project** - *Maria Nijnik, SIMRA Coordinator, The James Hutton Institute UK*

16.40 - 18.00 **Stakeholder introductions** - *David Miller, The James Hutton Institute UK*

18.00 - 19.20 Dynamics in Social Innovation: Enabling Factors and Barriers

Invited speaker: *Susan Baker, Cardiff University*

19.30 - 22.00 Dinner: Restaurant AQA in surroundings of the Slovak University of Technology

27.10. 2016 Thursday

location: Devín - Slovak - Austrian cross border: Hotel Hradná Brána

8.15 - 9.30 Departure to Devín

(bus departs from Slovak University of Technology, Vazovova 5 at 8.15)

9.30 - 13.30 Social Innovations in Marginalised Rural Areas - chair: *David Miller, James Hutton Institute UK*

9.30 - 10.30 Social Innovations in Marginalised Rural Areas (MRA) - deliberative discussion on **stakeholder survey** - *Veronika Gežík, SPECTRA, Institute of Forest Ecology, Slovak Academy of Sciences*

10.30 - 11.00 Coffee Break

11.00 - 12.15 Understanding and assessing social innovations and MRA

Stakeholder consultations I – breakout groups (WP2 + WP3)

12.15 - 12.45 **Reporting to the plenary: Stakeholder consultations I**

12.45 - 13.30 **Introduction to the SIMRA communication** - WP7

13.30 - 14.30 Lunch

14.30 - 15.00 Cross border MRA: Isolation or cooperation? Short walk to the confluence of Dunaj and Morava rivers

15.00 - 19.00 Social Innovations in Marginalised Rural Areas - chair: *Maria Nijnik, SIMRA Coordinator, James Hutton Institute UK*

- 15.00 - 16.40 Understanding and assessing social innovations and MRA **Stakeholder consultations II** - breakout groups (WP2 + WP3)
- 16.40 - 17.00 Break
- 17.00 - 18.30 **Stakeholder consultations III (WP5):** Introduction to SIMRA case studies
- 18.30 - 19.00 **Summary of Sessions I and II - Plenary discussion**
- 19.00 Dinner and local wine tasting
- 22.00 Transport back to hotels (bus leaves at 22.00)

28.10. 2016 Friday

location: Slovak University of Technology, Vazovova 5, 812 43, Bratislava

- 8.15 - 13.30 Evaluation and Policies** – chair: *Martin Price, Centre for Mountain Studies University of the Highlands and Islands (to be confirmed)*
- 8.15 - 10.15 **Stakeholder consultations IV (WP4):** Frameworks, methods and tools to assess social innovation and its impacts assessing
- 10.15 - 10.30 Break
- 10.30 - 12.00 **Stakeholder consultations V (WP6):** Policies and supporting actions for Social Innovation
- 12.00 - 12.30 **Summary of Sessions III, IV + V**
- 13.00 - 13.30 Closing remarks
- 13.30 - 14.30 Lunch

Annex C: Results of SIMRA short survey of stakeholders' perception of social innovation

WP2 – Theoretical and operational frameworks to understand social innovations (SI) in rural areas

Task 2.3 – Operationalizing stakeholders' engagement in SIMRA

The survey was sent to SITT members of SIMRA project.

Total invitations: 34

Responses: 24 (23 complete, 1 partial)

Responses volume

Q1: From your perspective what do you perceive as social innovation? Please provide a definition and/or give an example of an interesting social innovation from your perspective.

DEFINITION: EFFECTIVITY

- An innovative way to address a social issue more effectively, efficiently and sustainably. Its value accrues mostly to the society.
- A novel solution to a social problem that is more effective, efficient, sustainable, or just than current solutions.
- A social innovation is a novel solution to a social problem that is more effective, efficient, sustainable, or just than current solutions. It is a new combination and/or new configuration of social practices in certain areas of action or social contexts.
- A social innovation is "a novel solution to a social problem that is more effective, efficient, sustainable, or just than existing solutions and for which the value created accrues primarily to society as a whole rather than private individuals" (Phills et al. cited in Hubert et. Al., 2010)

- *A social innovation is a sociological solution to a social problem that is more effective, efficient, sustainable, or just than current solutions. The value created accrues primarily to society rather than to private individuals. For example, creating social policies to combat child labour. ILO-IPEC experience in Turkey reveals that for a successful campaign against child labour, the problem needs to be approached holistically and comprehensively. In fact, elimination of child labour and the national goal of achieving universal basic education for girls and boys are inherently linked since the former has the potential of being a key obstacle for the latter.*
- *A novel solution to a social problem that is more effective, efficient, sustainable than current solutions. The value created accrues primarily to society rather than to private individuals. Examples include consumers' improved trust towards fair trade products*

DEFINITION: NEW SOCIAL IDEAS

- *New ideas for social value*
- *A new model for new social strategies*
- *SI is all the thoughts and ideas helping people to live better life*
- *Applying a new approach to the way groups of people are organized around a certain subject*
- *New ideas, concepts and their application that meets social needs of stakeholders/population of area in question*
- *SI is a partial of radical improvement/innovation in social area (crowdfunding, for example, medical care or education through internet)*
- *Finding new ways of overcoming marginalisation and exclusion for a variety of reasons relating to human relationships, hierarchies, and organisations etc. which are not purely economic in character.*

DEFINITION: SOCIAL NEEDS/EDUCATION

- *New ways/ideas/projects to meet the social needs and/or challenges. As an example I will give one which is "dear" to me: innovative strategies in school for youngsters*
- *Approaches that can promote socio-economic development on the actual conditions and restrictions. Ex :Integration of students with special needs in farm activities*

DEF AND EXAMPLES: GOVERNANCE

- *I perceive social innovation like an develop multi-actor projects and thematic networks genuinely involving*

- *A change on the approach on the relation of people at community level focused on improving participation, equity and other characteristics of good governance*
- *Social innovation is perceived as new forms of communication, social relations and collaboration between actors and different sectors of a given sphere of influence. In order to provide solutions to need which have not been satisfied, which are not resolved by social local political structures or, they don't have a satisfactory solution with current infrastructure.*
- *SI is committed to initiatives that are catalysts for social change, from a creative and effective perspective, for a complex or simple answer.*
- *Social innovation is based on new systems of organizations, planning and specially cooperation: feel part, using new tools, services and processes and ways of thinking in the field of social science.*
- *1.1 Leader methodology and social innovation in rural areas.*
- *In rural social architecture the decision making power has not been assigned to the private sector and civil society, but in their favour, new social networks are having more influence on the rural development policy. Thus, an institutional reform should be required to empower and provide skills to their regions, sub regions and local authorities. Mainly, giving the local action group wide margins of freedom and flexibility to make decisions and implement measures. The stakeholders of a territory are the most motivated agents to analyse their own problems and try to find the most appropriate solutions. They have also a deep knowledge of the territory, but might need certain technical support, to find a more realistic and appropriate strategy of territorial development.*
- *The LEADER method is itself an innovation in rural areas, which puts people at the centre of the development process, their needs and their knowledge, and promotes their participation in decision making.*
- *Innovation in rural areas consists of: - the ability to exploit local resources that have not been exploited yet or have not been adequately used or even have been abandoned.*
- *Identify and support groups able to make proposals and projects that had not been done before and facilitate their learning process, whether to develop and market products or services.*
- *The ability to take the risk of experimentation and change, promoting entrepreneurship and responsibility of agents in all phases of the process and facilitating their access to new knowledge and technologies.*
- *Social innovations in the context of rural development are perceived by me as private civil initiatives as to improvement of rural life, they appear and develop at the local level in rural communities and provide the multiplicative influence on the economic development of community and the territory. Self-organization of rural communities is made by developing*

and implementing of social innovations and social partnership in the villages. Nowadays, social innovations which are or will be suitable for Ukraine: sustainable or environment friendly agricultural production; local food systems; maintain the biodiversity, ecosystems (e.g. agroecosystems; forest ecosystems) and landscapes; renewables (e.g. bioenergy); ecosystem services (int. al. tourism) and recreation services; can be provided by the social innovations based on the agricultural production and other rural activities.

- *Social innovation (SI) is a process, movement, research or network in the public sector. It tackles the problems of how to improve society's capacities and how to solve society's dilemmas. SI is interrelated with other innovation processes, like technological, environmental (climate), scientific and economic. It is seen as the newest category of innovations increasingly developing with growing needs and problems emerging in society. SI is carried out within NGOs, associations, social enterprises, public policy and also science.*

EXAMPLES: AGRICULTURE

- *Sustainable agriculture adapted with climate change*
- *Social innovation seen on 2 different domains: i) public administration and ii) the public at large about Commons, the attribution by law from traditional organization to more dynamic agencies of managerial powers (Italy); ii) the re-birth of Co-operative farmers' enterprises on self-determined management for growing, harvesting, processing and marketing of their produce (Georgia)*
- *Social innovation is a new idea/organization/... (or the application of an existing one to another area/territory) that meet any social need. For instance, the developing of new ways of relationship between farmers and consumers could be an interesting social innovation, but also the development of new strategies of agricultural management and wildlife aimed to strengthen coexistence between the livestock activity and biodiversity conservation*
- *Social farming is an example of innovation process that brings to co-production of knowledge, goods, social services, wellbeing on the basis of cooperation of different actors and sectors. Social Farm presume the formation of new networks and relations between producers, consumers and other actors of the supply chain, territorially organized social/health services, local authorities and Institutions. Social Farming implies the combination of private and public actors and the interaction between Agriculture, social, health, educational, employment Policies and actors. As part of multifunctional farming, it can offer a wide range of services aimed at pursuing the well-being of citizenry, and responds to the wider needs of welfare policies. In general SF objectives may be divided into agricultural and non-agricultural objectives. Agricultural objectives are directly connected with agricultural production, farming*

methods and protection of environment against negative impacts of agricultural activities. Non-agricultural objectives may comprise the quality of life in rural areas, improving the quality of social services, promoting the use of local resources, protecting and maintaining the traditional living, working heritage, promoting social justice. SF is based on collective learning process in which different social groups and actors participate and which results in new skills and practices as well as in new attitudes, values, behaviours and governance mechanism, a transition towards sustainable agriculture and rural and urban development.

Q2: On a scale from 1 to 5 how do you assess the relative importance of social innovation in delivering improved rural development outcomes in marginalized rural areas?

Answer Choices	Responses
1 - unimportant	0.00% 0
2 - rather unimportant	0.00% 0
3 - rather important	4.17% 1
4 - important	25.00% 6
5 - very important	70.83% 17
Total	24

Q3: In your opinion, what are the three most important societal challenges that marginalized rural areas face?

EDUCATION AND EMPLOYMENT

- Education and employment
- Education
- Level of education in rural population
- Quality of education and high rates of dropout in schools
- The need to increase the level of education and professional orientation of rural population, study of the modern world and domestic experience;
- Lack of possibilities for employment /jobs)
- Improving possibility of local people for employment
- Employment - income, social security
- Employment through internet

POVERTY

- Poverty & deprivation,
- Poverty and social exclusion,
- Lack of sufficient resources (financial) and incentives to address poverty,
- Poverty and food insecurity
- Decreasing the number of people in or at risk of poverty and social exclusion

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC EXCLUSION

- Growing gap between incomes and 'normal' social aspiration,
- Difficulty (physical, but not only) in getting close to the core of society,
- Cultural remoteness to follow new trends and technological Innovations
- Weakness of awareness of the civil society
- Increase rural-urban reciprocity
- Limited opportunities for young people
- Limited opportunities for young people
- Gender inequality
- Be attractive for population (work, access, conditions, ...)
- Inequalities based on regional disparities (ex: aging, child labour, proletarianization in informal economy
- Low economy
- Slow democratic (vs traditional) progress in implementing at local level more balanced interpersonal relationships

- Inability to turn perceived 'positives' of such areas into tangible benefits for the local population
- no sustainable value to their production
- Changes to emphasize the importance of local: influence in tiers of government to respect the dynamics of endogenous development. Provision of sufficient funds to finance the lack of services and thus reduce the gap between urban and rural. Assess rural areas for their support and close cooperation in mitigating climate change; rural inhabitants are guardians of ecosystems and the pantry of the cities.
- Ecosystem services (fresh air, water, biodiversity regarding plants and animals)
- Combine economic goals with social objectives
- Expectation (and tacit acceptance) of political and economic marginalisation
- Lack of political power / influence
- Social and cultural marginalization of young generation
- Lack of self-appreciation & lack of recognition of the role of rural areas to solve our current socio-economic and environmental challenges
- Communication
- Understand the value of doing together,
- Creating conditions for driving forces: exchange of ideas and values, shift in roles and relationships and integration of private capital with public and philanthropic support

POPULATION

- Depopulation and ageing
- Ageing
- Changes to face global factors that impact local: aging of the population, depopulation areas, keep Young people in the territory (bring down unemployment),
- Massive youth outflow from rural area,
- Depopulation / ageing, education, absence of political wheel
- Depopulation (consequence related to the previous)
- Demographic change

ENTREPRENEURSHIP

- Changes in entrepreneurship: improve cooperation and internal relations, thus increasing the resilience of the territories. Reduce dependence on public sector. Encourage private investment.
- Insufficient amount of programs to support business initiatives, innovative ideas and programs from agriculture cluster development.

- Limited opportunities to promote skills for entrepreneurship

SERVICES AND INFRASTRUCTURE

- Poor access to services (schools, health care)
- Relatively poor access to services
- Access to school, sanitary and other services
- Housing
- Health care
- Lack of social and economic resources & services
- Food and energy (firewood, crop residuals, etc. for cooking and heating)
- Sustainable access to energy and natural resources
- Healthcare
- Difficult access to supply chain
- Limited or non-existent public services and infrastructure
- Digital divide - biased ICT infrastructure
- Internet of services
- Also a service, but particularly slow / poor internet

ENVIRONMENT AND SUSTAINABILITY

- Sustainable agriculture and forestry
- Wellbeing, health, sustainable environment
- Reach sustainability

SECURITY

- Secure societies,
- Food security

Q4 : In your opinion, what are the most relevant factors that influence the emergence of social innovations in marginalized rural areas? Please grade the importance of the factors listed below on a scale from 0 to 5, and/or provide your suggestion.

Scale: 1 – unimportant 2- rather unimportant 3 - rather important 4 – important 5 - very important

Answered: 25 Skipped: 0

	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Weighted Average
Ecological (resource use (overuse), biodiversity)	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	20.83% 5	62.50% 15	16.67% 4	24	3.96
Economic (efficiency, cohesion, competitiveness)	4.17% 1	0.00% 0	29.17% 7	37.50% 9	29.17% 7	24	3.88
Investment (funding) activities in the area	4.17% 1	4.17% 1	16.67% 4	45.83% 11	29.17% 7	24	3.92
Social (equity, social capital)	0.00% 0	8.33% 2	16.67% 4	25.00% 6	50.00% 12	24	4.17
Conflicts of user and decision makers	0.00% 0	8.33% 2	29.17% 7	50.00% 12	12.50% 3	24	3.67
Sustainability and resilience of the regions	4.17% 1	4.17% 1	41.67% 10	8.33% 2	41.67% 10	24	3.79
Participatory processes	4.17% 1	4.17% 1	8.33% 2	33.33% 8	50.00% 12	24	4.21
Self – organizing activities (bottom up)	8.33% 2	0.00% 0	16.67% 4	20.83% 5	54.17% 13	24	4.13
Monitoring and sanctioning of legal compliance	4.17% 1	25.00% 6	29.17% 7	37.50% 9	4.17% 1	24	3.13

Comments:

- Willingness to change and skills and knowledge to enable innovations are key factors too
- Gender inequality
- Land use, free access to forests and other land, governance
- Culture and respect
- Increasing levels of education of local people: re-education courses, innovative forms of education at regional education, increase the motivation of adults to educate, social innovation at the workplace
- Remember "internet revolution" (Industry 4.0) as challenge and risk for these areas
- The necessity to have a systemic approach
- The blast of the international crisis with the sharply rising of poverty all over Europe, the crisis of welfare state were at the bottom of new form of social innovation such as social farming and the Social and solidarity economy able to combine protection of environment and valorisation of human being.
- Cultural erosion, and disappearance of a way of life

Q5 : Based on your experience, how would you grade (on a scale from 0 to 5) the importance of assessing social innovation and the type of method most appropriate for use in its evaluation?

Scale: 1- unimportant 2- rather unimportant 3 - rather important 4 – important 5 - very important

	1	2	3	4	5	Total	Weighted Average
assessment of how social innovation is organized and implemented	4.35% 1	8.70% 2	0.00% 0	39.13% 9	47.83% 11	23	4.17
assessment of effects of social innovation	4.35% 1	4.35% 1	0.00% 0	13.04% 3	78.26% 18	23	4.57
qualitative methods	0.00% 0	4.35% 1	26.09% 6	43.48% 10	26.09% 6	23	3.91
quantitative methods	8.70% 2	17.39% 4	21.74% 5	34.78% 8	17.39% 4	23	3.35
mix (quali-quantitative) methods	0.00% 0	4.35% 1	13.04% 3	17.39% 4	65.22% 15	23	4.43

Annex D: General overview of the consultation activities for 2017

Process of engagement	Means of engagement	Stakeholders included	Partner responsible	Connection to other WP	Deliverable (D) /Milestone (MS)	Deadline	Timing of consultation
Launch of digital web based platforms for online consultations		All	IAMZ -CIHEAM	WP1, WP2, WP7	MS10	M9	To run to M10
Examples for online database	Web based platform: submission box	All	Perth College	WP3	D3.2 MS13	M12	M10-11
Innovative SES models based on SI variables	Web platform consultation 1	SITT	IFE SAS	WP2 , WP3, WP4, WP5	D2.2	M16	M13
Draft list of variables explaining diverging paths of SI (to be presented to SITT)	Web platform consultation 1	SITT	Perth College +IFE SAS	WP2, WP3, WP5	MS14	M16	M13
Selection of criteria/ preferences of CS	Web platform consultation 1	SITT	EFI	WP5			M13
Short listed SI CSs, and policy processes identified	Web-platform consultation 1	SITT	Perth College	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	MS15	M16	M13
Preliminary set of methods to assess SI and its impacts	Web-platform consultation 1 to follow analysis of existing methods	SITT	UNIPD	WP4, WP2		Not pre-defined	M13
Pilot set of methods to assess impacts / implications of SI in selected CS and policy processes	Web-platform consultation 2	SITT and CS members	UNIPD	WP4, WP2, WP5 and WP6	MS20	M24	M18-20
Policy implications for SI in MRAs	Web- platform consultation 2 or	All and a selection of	BOKU	WP6	MS6.2: Consultation on	M30	M18-20

	Survey Monkey (in line with the project): 6 questions and 1 short text for association	policy relevant stakeholders			results from 6.1 to prepare for 6.2		
SIMRA SITT Workshop (WS) II	Face-to-face	SITT and (potentially) key members of stakeholder group 3	IFE SAS	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	MS11	M30	M23 or later – to launch at a SIMRA meeting
Completion of preliminary set of guidelines and recommendations for policy cases (to be presented to SITT)	Face-to-face interactions (presentation & discussion)	SITT and key members from stakeholder group 3 (if together with SIMRA WS II)	RDC	WP2, WP6	MS28, D6.3	M40	Following M36 (if preferable: together with MS11, above)
Completion of final guidelines and recommendations for policy and practice target groups finalized	Online 3: draft guidelines for comments (e-mail reminder and host on platform)	Policy and Practice	BOKU	WP6	MS29	M46	M40-42 (before launch of the guides)
Local stakeholder workshops	Face-to-face	Stakeholder groups 2 and 3	HUTTON & Euromontana	WP1, WP2, WP5, WP7	MS33	M30-42	M17-36
Workshop on lessons learned from IA implementation	Face-to-face	Selected members of the SIB	EFI	WP5, WP7	MS34	M43	M30-36